

**Flavonoids and other Constituents of
Sterculia Genus**

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STERCULIA foetida Linn. (Sterculaceae) possesses medicinal properties¹. Earlier studies² on this plant have reported a number of compounds like procyanidin-3-*O*- β -D-glucoside, isocutellarin and 6-glucuronosyloxyluteolin, two rare tetramethyl ethers of quercetin, sterculic acid, malvalic acid and a number of fatty acids.

The air-dried stem of *S. foetida* Linn. (collected from the surroundings of Rewa, M.P.) was powdered and extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene and ethyl acetate successively. The concentrated ethyl acetate extract deposited an orange solid, which on column chromatography over silica gel furnished Compound-A, on elution with acetone. A buff coloured solid was obtained on addition of petroleum ether to the filtrate, after removal of the orange-red solid. It was characterised as leucoanthocyanidin-3-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranoside. The remaining filtrate, on further concentration, yielded another orange-coloured solid, which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel and eluted successively with benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 2) and benzene-ethyl acetate-methanol (2 : 1 : 1), giving Compound-B and Compound-C respectively.

Compound-A was crystallised from acetone-methanol (1 : 1, v/v) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 316°, and characterised as quercetin by usual spectral analysis.

Compound-B was crystallised from MeOH as yellow solid, m.p. 181° (Found : C, 56.29; H, 4.51. C₂₁H₂₀O₁₁ calcd. for : C, 56.25; H, 4.48%); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 253 and 370 nm (flavanoid glycoside); ν_{\max} 1 110–1 010 cm⁻¹ (glycosidic linkage); the methyl ether *m/z* 358 (*M*⁺, 100%), 343 (*M*-CH₃), 329 (*M*-HCHO), 180 and 179 (RDA fragments), the fragments of *m/z* 329 and 179 confirmed OH group at C-3; pmr spectrum showed expected signals due to rhamnosyl group and for flavanoid. On acid hydrolysis with 7% ethanolic H₂SO₄, it gave an aglycone, m.p. 316°, which was identified as quercetin. The aqueous part on working up showed the presence of rhamnose. Hence, Compound-B was characterised as monorhamnoside of quercetin.

Compound-C was crystallised from MeOH as light yellow amorphous solid, m.p. 184°d, which could not be characterised.

Sterculia urens Roxb.¹ (Sterculaceae) was collected from the forests of Rajnandgaon, M.P. Earlier communications on this plant have reported a number of compounds³.

Air-dried and powdered roots of the plant (6 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether. The defatted

roots were extracted with ethanol, concentrated and added to a large volume of water which was finally extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was chromatographed over silica gel. It was eluted with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (2 : 4, v/v) to afford a brown coloured solid. It was dissolved in aqueous NaOH, kept overnight, precipitated with dilute HCl and recrystallised from MeOH, m.p. 204-05°. It was characterised as 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin from spectral analysis.

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